

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF MOWRAH FLOWERS
(*B. LATIFOLIA*). PART I. PROXIMATE COMPOSITION

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Mowrah tree is one of the most important forest trees of India. The fleshy corollas of its flowers are either eaten raw or cooked or are dried, ground and mixed with flour for making cakes. The yield of flowers from a single tree is about 150-300 lbs. per season.

Church¹, Elsworth², Ruediger³ and Fowler *et al.*⁴ have examined these flowers. Mande *et al.*⁵ have studied the alcoholic fermentation of *Bassia* flowers and reported that these flowers contained 18.4% moisture, 5.9% protein and 70.0% reducing sugar as glucose. The present work was undertaken to throw more light on the chemical composition of mowrah (*Bassia latifolia*) flowers as regards sugars, protein, fat and minerals.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Sugars.—Different sugars were detected by means of paper partition chromatography using the descending technique of Partridge⁶ with *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5) as an irrigating solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as a spraying reagent with a 'multiple development' technique of Jeanes *et al.*⁷, and after six such developments, an excellent resolution of a mixture of sugars was effected.

Reducing sugars (before and after hydrolysis) were estimated by Cole's method⁸. Fructose was determined by a colorimetric method of Englis and Miles⁹, and pentoses by the method of Fernell and King¹⁰.

By extracting twice with hot water, sugars present in the mowrah flowers were removed to the extent of 98%.

The following sugars, as recorded in Table I, were detected from the unhydrolysed and hydrolysed extracts. With the 'multiple development' technique, the R_f values obtained were quite different from those given in the literature, but they varied in a definite proportion, and the sugars followed the same order. The unknown sugars from the extracts were detected by comparing the R_f values with those of the reference.

TABLE I

Known sugars.	R_F .	<i>Unknown (i.e. extracts)</i>				
		Unhydrolysed.			Hydrolysed.	
		R_F .	Inference.		R_F .	Inference.
1. Maltose	0.31	1. 0.31	Maltose	1. 0.31		Maltose
2. Sucrose	0.40	2. 0.40	Sucrose	2. 0.48		Galacturonic acid*
3. D-Galactose	0.55	3. 0.57	Glucose	3. 0.57		Glucose
4. D-Glucose	0.57	4. 0.62	Arabinose	4. 0.62		Arabinose
5. D-Arabinose	0.52	5. 0.65	Fructose	5. 0.65		Fructose
6. D-Fructose	0.66	6. 0.81	Rhamnose*	6. 0.81		Rhamnose*
7. D-Xylose	0.69					

Inferred from Partridge⁶.

Amino-acids.—Mowrah flowers were hydrolysed by autoclaving with 3 N-HCl at 15 lb. p. s. i. pressure for 10 hours. After cooling, the hydrolysate was neutralised with 3 N-NaOH and filtered. This filtrate was used for the detection of the presence of various amino-acids and for the estimation of amino-acid-% nitrogen and total amino-acids.

The aforesaid method of Partridge⁶ was followed for the detection of amino-acids from the protein hydrolysate with the same solvent. Ninhydrin¹¹ was used as a spraying reagent¹¹ and the chromatogram was made permanent with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ reagent. After three developments⁷ a satisfactory separation of amino-acids was effected.

The paper chromatography of the protein hydrolysate of mowrah flowers revealed the presence of eleven amino-acids (Table II).

TABLE II

No.	Known amino-acids.	R_F .	Hydrolysate (unknown).		
			No.	R_F .	Inference.
I	Lysine	0.29	I	0.29	Lysine
II	Histidine	0.32	II	0.35	Arginine
III	Arginine	0.36	III	0.46	Aspartic acid
IV	Glycine	0.40	IV	0.50	Threonine
V	Aspartic acid	0.47	V	0.56	Glutamic acid
VI	Threonine	0.50	VI	0.66	Valine
VII	Alanine	0.60	VII	0.83	Tryptophane
VIII	Valine	0.67	VIII	0.86	Phenylalanine
IX	Methionine	0.79	XI	0.90	isoLeucine
X	Tryptophane	0.84	X	0.94	Leucine
XI	Phenylalanine	0.86			
XII	isoLeucine	0.90			
XIII	Leucine	0.93			

** Inferred from Block *et al.* (Paper Chromatography. Academic Press Inc., N. Y., 1952).

The chromatogram also showed the presence of proline which gave yellow spot (faint) with ninhydrin. On spraying with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ reagent, it

turned very faint green and finally disappeared. The unhydrolysed sample did not show any spot on the paper, indicating the absence of free amino-acid.

Total nitrogen content was determined by the usual Kjeldahl's method. Amino-acid- α nitrogen and total amino-acids were estimated according to the methods suggested by Hardin and MacLean¹³ and Spies and Chambers¹³ respectively.

Fat.—Fat was extracted with diethyl ether and then taken up in light petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°). Iodine values of the fat as such and of mixed fatty acids were determined by Wij's method. The spectra of the unsaponifiable matter and the fatty acids were also taken on a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, DU Model, in the ultraviolet region of light from 230 to 340 m μ .

The paper chromatography of fatty acids in the form of hydroxamates was also carried out according to Inouye and Noda¹⁴. The colour which was given on the chromatogram by FeCl₃ solution, could also be developed in a test tube. The hydroxamate solutions of standards and unknown were diluted with ethanol, colour developed with FeCl₃ solution and their spectra taken on the same spectrophotometer in the visible range of light from 400 to 650 m μ .

The paper chromatography of the hydroxamates of fatty acids of mowrah flower fat indicated the presence of four fatty acids. The paper was irrigated in *n*-butanol—acetic acid for 18 hours and the chromatogram sprayed with 1% alcoholic FeCl₃ solution. Table III shows the presence of four acids.

TABLE III

No.	Known fatty acids.		No.	Unknown (mowrah flower fat).	
	Acids.	R _F .		R _F .	Inference.
1.	Acetic	0.50	1.	0.90	Linoleic
2.	Butyric	0.61	2.	0.92	Oleic
3.	Oleic	0.92	3.	0.93	Palmitic
4.	Stearic	0.94	4.	0.94	Stearic

The R_F values given by Inouye and Noda¹⁴ were used to infer the presence of palmitic and linoleic acids.

For confirmation of the identity of the saturated fatty acids, 1.65 g. of the mixed fatty acids from mowrah fat in 10 volumes of ether was maintained for 6 hours at 0°. The insoluble portion obtained was filtered and dried in vacuum. The soluble portion was then crystallised at -30° for 6 hours, filtered and dried in vacuum. The insoluble fractions obtained at 0° and -30° melted between (i) 68°-71° and (ii) 66°-68° respectively. The melting points of pure stearic and palmitic acids are 69.6° and 63.1° respectively. From the melting point-composition diagram for the binary

systems of palmitic-stearic acid (Schutte and Vogel¹⁰) the presence of palmitic acid along with stearic acid can be confirmed in both the insoluble fractions at 0° and -30°, obtained from the mixed fatty acids of mowrah flower fat.

Minerals.—Ash, calcium, iron, magnesium, phosphorus and copper were determined in the dried mowrah flowers. The determinations of ash, calcium and magnesium were carried out according to the method as given in A. O. A. C. (VII Ed., 1950). Phosphorus and iron were estimated according to the methods given by Sterges, Hardin and McLutire¹⁵ and Moss and Mellon¹⁶ respectively. Chilton's procedure¹⁷ was followed for the determination of copper.

Analysis of mowrah flowers.—Table IV shows the percentage composition of mowrah flowers.

TABLE IV

Moisture	21.6%	Protein (on dry wt. basis) :	Minerals :	
Fat	1.3	Total N content	Ash	2.59%
Sugars (on dry wt. basis) :		Total amino-acid-N	Phosphorus	0.13
Total sugar	89.7	Amino-acid-N (α)	Iron	0.03
Reducing sugar	66.2	Non-protein-N	Calcium	0.25
Invert sugar	23.5	Crude protein (N $\times$ 6.25)	Magnesium	0.21
Fructose	15.3	Total amino-acids	Copper	0.002
Pentoses (arabinose-		Amino-acids (α -N)	Residue (insoluble in	
rhamnose)	3.3	Amino-acids (other than	HCl <i>i.e.</i> sand and	
		α -N)	silica)	0.83

The iodine value of the mixed fatty acids of the mowrah flower was found to be 96.9, indicating that the fat contained very little of highly unsaturated fatty acids. The spectra of the mixed fatty acids show a peak at 270 $m\mu$. The fatty acids were alkali-isomerised with ethylene glycol and the absorption spectra of the isomerised samples (Table V) showed two peaks, one at 234 $m\mu$ and the other at 268 $m\mu$, indicating the presence of di- and tri-ethenoid fatty acids in the fat. This confirmed the presence of linoleic acid which was indicated from the paper chromatographic study.

TABLE V

Absorption spectra of alkali-isomerised sample of fatty acids from mowrah flower.

Dieneic acid.		Trieneic acid.	
Wave-length.	Optical density.	Wave-length.	Optical density.
230 $m\mu$	0.345	260 $m\mu$	0.122
232	0.352	262	0.126
234	0.356	264	0.134
236	0.343	266	0.142
238	0.317	268	0.146
240	0.298	270	0.133

The fat as such gave an iodine value of 90.4.

DISCUSSION

In the quantitative analysis, the values obtained for reducing and total sugars were more or less in agreement with those obtained by Shroff¹⁰ except that his values for fructose were high. Higher values than those of Fowler *et al.*⁴ were obtained for pentoses. The presence of higher saccharides and not sucrose in mowrah flowers, as noted by Walawalkar¹⁰, could not be confirmed. The paper partition chromatography definitely showed the presence of sucrose in the unhydrolysed extract.

Out of the total nitrogen content, total amino-acid-nitrogen is 83.5%, while non-protein nitrogen is only 16.5%. Amino-acid- α -nitrogen in the total nitrogen content is 67%. The difference in the total amino-acid-nitrogen and amino-acid- α -nitrogen contents may be due to proline and/or hydroxyproline content.

FIG. 1

Absorption spectra of hydroxamates of fatty acids and fatty acids of mowrah flowers.

Curves I-V refer respectively to acetic, butyric, oleic and stearic acid and fatty acids of mowrah flower fat.

The lower fatty acids, like acetic and butyric, showed distinct and deep coloured spots on the paper chromatogram. Spots of oleic and stearic acids were not so deep coloured but were easily detectable. The spots given by the fatty acid mixture did not show such an easy and well-defined separation. The R_F values for the above acids in the present work are slightly different from those reported by Inouye and Noda.¹⁴ It was observed that the R_F values increased with the increase in the number of carbon atoms and also in the molecular weights (*i.e.* from acetic to stearic acids).

The absorption spectra of the hydroxamates of the standard acids with $FeCl_3$ was compared with those of the fatty acids of mowrah flower fat. Fig. 1 shows that acetic acid gives two peaks (at 470 $m\mu$ and 520 $m\mu$). Oleic acid and butyric acid, however, show only one maximum at 500 and 495 $m\mu$ respectively. In order to study the effect of time factor on the intensity of the colour development, readings, after the development of colour, were taken after $\frac{1}{2}$, 10, 24 hours and also after several days. It was observed that there was no change in the intensity of the colour on standing. The mowrah flower fatty acid hydroxamates on similar treatment gave two peaks, one at 510 $m\mu$ and the other at 475 $m\mu$. The peak at 510 $m\mu$ may be due to presence of stearic and oleic acids.

The ash content of the mowrah flowers was found to be 2.6% and was in conformity with the findings of Ruediger⁴ though other workers¹⁻² reported ash percentage from 3.5 to 5. No data are available on the mineral contents of mowrah flowers. Out of the minerals examined, calcium was present in large amount and magnesium in an appreciable quantity.

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S U M M A R Y

The paper chromatography of sugars reveals the presence of sucrose, maltose, glucose, fructose, arabinose and rhamnose in the unhydrolysed extract of mowrah flowers. In the hydrolysed extract, only sucrose is absent and one more spot indicated the presence of galacturonic acid.

Different amino-acids present in the mowrah flowers are lysine, arginine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, threonine, valine, tryptophane, phenylalanine, isoleucine, leucine and proline. They are present not in free forms but in the form of proteins.

The paper chromatography of fatty acids and the spectra of hydroxamates indicate the presence of oleic, palmitic, stearic and linoleic acids in the fat of mowrah flowers.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Church, *Nature*, 1886, **33**, 343.
2. Elsworthby, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1887, **6**, 21.
3. Ruediger, *Chem. Abst.*, 1913, **7**, 3389.
4. Fowler *et al.*, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1920, **3**, 81.
5. Mande *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, **41**, 1451.
6. Partridge, *Biochem. J.*, 1948, **42**, 238. *Nature*, 1949, **164**, 443.
7. Jeanes *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 415.
8. Cole, *Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 723.
9. Englis & Miles, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 583.
10. Fernell & King, *Analyst*, 1953, **78**, 80.
11. Conden *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1944, **38**, 224.
12. Hardin & McLean, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1915, **20**, 217.
13. Spies & Chambers, *ibid.*, 1951, **191**, 787.
14. Inouye & Noda, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1949, **23**, 291.
15. Sterges, Hardin & McIntire, *J. Assoc. Offg. Agric. Chem.*, 1950, **33**, 114.
16. Moss & Mellon, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1942, **14**, 862.
17. Chilton, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 1274.
18. Shroff, M.Sc. Thesis., Bombay University, 1947.
19. Walawalkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 667.
20. Schutte & Vogel, *Oil & Soap*, 1940, **17**, 155.